

EFFECT OF HUMIDITY AND IRRIGATION INDICATORS ON THE
BIOPOTENTIAL OF LOCAL TREES IN THE CONDITIONS OF KHOREZM
REGION

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Abstract: *Khorezm region is one of the most arid and water-scarce regions of Uzbekistan. Indicators such as climate humidity and irrigation play an important role in the normal growth and development of trees. Nowadays, drip irrigation is widely used in agriculture along with drip irrigation.*

Key words: *climate indicators, irrigation methods, evaporation, leaf area, water use.*

Nowadays, the large-scale impact of anthropogenic factors has led to changes in all natural processes in ecosystems. The aggravation of the ecological situation, the negative changes in the atmosphere, soil, groundwater and surface waters require urgent measures to protect the natural environment and the proper organization of rational use of nature.

Saline soils are an important component of both natural and anthropogenic landscapes in arid regions. Salinity is one of the main genetic traits of arid soils and is a trait that limits fertility [1,3,4,5].

The main criterion for assessing the physical condition of the soil is the compliance of the set of soil properties with the characteristics of the functions performed by the soil in a particular landscape [1,5]. Therefore, the issues of quantitative assessment of saline soils are of the greatest relevance. So, first of all, it is necessary to determine how and to what extent the amount of salts affects the performance of its ecological functions through the physical transformation of the soil [3].

With any method of irrigation, regardless of the method of moisture distribution in the area, the processes of absorption and formation of soil moisture reserves are determined by the characteristics of this soil. The water absorption of the soil, its conversion into a factor of fertility, and the depth of wetting depend on the water-physical properties of the soil.

The dependence of evaporation on various atmospheric phenomena makes it difficult to calculate, but we have seen that it depends on air temperature, relative humidity, light. From these we have seen that not only atmospheric phenomena but also the physiological

properties of the tree affect evaporation. The presence of salts in the soil and water reduces WU (water use), which may also be a key criterion in selecting trees to be planted in saline soils in Khorezm conditions.

The soil salinity examined during the study had little effect on the evaporation of the trees, *Elaeagnus an.* and *Ulmus p.* evaporation norms are lower in sand than in clayey soils, which indicates that they are not sensitive to soil and groundwater salinity.

Many studies have considered only surface parts and leaves when studying WUE (water use effective). This may be due to difficulties in studying root fractions. A significant difference in this magnitude was observed when the species took root DM (dry meter) into account. These observations show that groundwater also plays a major role in the assessment of tree WUE.

Differentiating trees according to WUE did not seem to differentiate them according to WU. Thus, WUE is important in determining the type of trees planted in arid lands, and in trees planted for biodegradation purposes, the WUE should be later, albeit small, when the WU is large. The reason we look at WUE as a key factor is that it helps maintain groundwater levels.

Figure 1. Indicators of surface and underground biomass development of trees.

In assessing the potential of different trees for saline soils in Khorezm conditions, water demand, salinity tolerance, and leaf formation of the tree should be taken into account based on field experiments. In three-year-old trees, the evaporating property of the leaf varies depending on the type. The water evaporating property of trees that grew when there was sufficient water in both soils was consistent with the development of their root system. The correlation of WU with LA (leaf area) was particularly characteristic of heterogeneous young trees.

The data obtained show that the trees studied under drip irrigation conditions develop a stronger root system, the use of drip irrigation allows not only to control the moisture regime in the root layer of the soil, but also to automate the irrigation process.

The main element that characterizes the irrigation regime of trees is the total water consumption. Depending on soil-climatic conditions and species of trees, the total water consumption has its own characteristics. Therefore, fertility cannot be considered separately from water availability. In areas with insufficient moisture, the need for water for sustainable production of trees significantly exceeds other necessary resources. Lack of moisture for good plant development is compensated by irrigation and precipitation during the entire growing season [2, 4, 6].

The effect of options on leaf and wood biomass development in other tree species was not statistically significant (Figure 1.)

Any changes that occur in the leaf should be considered as a reaction of the plant organism to man-made influences. When the full capacity of the body is overfilled, a breakdown occurs, which, as a rule, has the opposite sign of change. The results of the various tests performed are mainly due to the different levels of contamination (composition, concentration, duration).

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